

EXPERIMENTS ON THE SYNTHESIS OF KETO-ACIDS.
 SYNTHESIS OF 2-*p*-METHOXYPHENYLCYCLO-
 PENTANONE-3-CARBOXYLIC ACID.

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2-(*p*-Methoxyphenyl)-cyclopentanone-3-carboxylic acid has been synthesised with a view to study a scheme of work for the synthesis of phenanthrene derivatives related to natural products.

Anisaldehyde cyanohydrin (I) is allowed to react with the sodium salt of ethyl cyanoacetate when the sodium derivative of ethyl $\alpha\beta$ -dicyano- β -(*p*-methoxyphenyl)-propionate (II) is obtained. It is allowed to react with ethyl β -chloropropionate when diethyl $\alpha\beta$ -dicyano- α -(*p*-methoxyphenyl)-*n*-butane- $\beta\delta$ -dicarboxylate (III) is obtained. When hydrolysed by means of sulphuric acid (20%) the latter yields α -(*p*-methoxyphenyl)-*n*-butane- $\alpha\beta\delta$ -tricarboxylic acid (IV), the triethyl ester of which undergoes cyclisation in presence of sodium in dry benzene to yield diethyl 2-(*p*-methoxyphenyl)-cyclopentanone-3:5-dicarboxylate (V, R=R'=CO₂Et). This ester on hydrolysis and decarboxylation yields 2-(*p*-methoxyphenyl)-cyclopentanone-3-carboxylic acid (V, R=CO₂H ; R'=H).

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

Anisaldehyde Cyanohydrin (I).—Anisaldehyde (60 g.) was added gradually to 200 c.c. of a solution of sodium bisulphite (250 g. of sodium bisulphite in 300 c.c. of water). The flask was shaken and cooled in ice during addition. The bisulphite compound was collected, washed with spirit (100 c.c.) and added gradually with stirring and cooling to a solution of potassium cyanide (60 g. of potassium cyanide in 90 c.c. of water). The heavy oil was then extracted with ether and washed successively with water, sodium bisulphite solution, water, sodium bicarbonate solution and finally with water. The ether solution was then dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and the solvent removed under reduced pressure at 30° with the addition of two drops of concentrated sulphuric acid. The resultant oil solidified on standing in the refrigerator and the solid was then ground with petroleum ether (b.p. 30-60°), filtered off, washed with petroleum ether and recrystallised from ether-petroleum ether mixture, m.p. 67°, yield 60-70%.

Diethyl $\alpha\beta$ -dicyano- α -(p-methoxyphenyl)-n-butane- $\beta\delta$ -dicarboxylate (III).—Ethyl cyanoacetate (96 g.) was added to an ice-cold solution of sodium (20 g.) in alcohol (240 c.c.) and anisaldehyde cyanohydrin (110 g.) was gradually added to the suspension of ethyl sodiocyanoacetate. Considerable heat was generated after each addition and it was found necessary to regulate the temperature by cooling in ice-water, and the clear red liquid was allowed to stand for 12 hours when the whole mass solidified to a red cake. The product of reaction was mixed with ethyl β -chloropropionate (106 g.) and after the initial reaction had abated was boiled under reflux for 15 hours. It was filtered and washed with dry ether. The filtrate was diluted with water and extracted with ether. The ethereal solution was washed with water, dried with calcium chloride and the solvent removed. The dicyano ester was distilled as a viscous liquid at 233-36°/4 mm., yield 45 g. (Found : C, 64.0 ; H, 6.3. $C_{16}H_{22}O_5N_2$ requires C, 63.6 ; H, 6.1 per cent).

α -(p-Methoxyphenyl)-n-butane- $\alpha\beta\delta$ -tricarboxylic Acid (IV).—A solution of the above cyano-ester (III, 40 g.) in concentrated sulphuric acid (45 c.c.) was diluted with water (320 c.c.) and refluxed for 50 hours on a sand-bath. After cooling, the mixture was diluted with water and extracted with ether and the ethereal extract was treated with sodium carbonate solution. On acidification of the carbonate solution, the acid was obtained in the form of a gum which was extracted with ether. After drying over anhydrous sodium sulphate, the ether was removed and the gummy acid was kept in a vacuum desiccator, when it solidified. It was crystallised

from hot water, m.p. 183° (rapid heating), yield 20 g. (Found: C, 57.1; H, 5.4; Equiv., 101. $C_{14}H_{16}O_7$ requires C, 56.7; H, 5.4 per cent. Equiv. 98.67).

The *triethyl ester* was obtained in an almost quantitative yield from the acid by the alcohol vapour method. [The acid (30 g.), absolute alcohol (100 c.c.), concentrated sulphuric acid (9 c.c.), 4 litres of vapourised alcohol (4.5 hours)]. After dilution with a large volume of water, the ester was extracted with ether, the ethereal extract shaken with sodium bicarbonate solution and washed again, dried with sodium sulphate and ether removed. It was distilled at $205-15^{\circ}/3$ mm., yield 28 g. (Found: C, 63.4; H, 6.9. $C_{20}H_{28}O_7$ requires C, 63.1; H, 7.3 per cent).

Diethyl 2-(p-Methoxyphenyl)-cyclopentanone-3:5-dicarboxylate (V, $R=R'=CO_2Et$).—A mixture of the foregoing ester (30 g.) and molecular sodium (3.6 g.) in dry benzene (75 c.c.) was refluxed for 10 minutes to start the reaction. The heating was discontinued until the vigour of the reaction abated and heating was then continued for 2 hours. After cooling, the product was treated with cold dilute sulphuric acid and the benzene layer washed with aqueous sodium bicarbonate and with water, dried and solvent removed. The residue in alcoholic solution gave a reddish violet colouration with ferric chloride. The ester distilled with much decomposition at $202-212^{\circ}/4$ mm., yield 6 g. (Found: C, 65.1; H, 6.3. $C_{18}H_{22}O_6$ requires C, 64.6; H, 6.5 per cent).

2-(p-Methoxyphenyl)-cyclopentanone-3-carboxylic Acid (V, $R=CO_2H$; $R'=H$).—The above ester (10 g.) was refluxed with excess of dilute sulphuric acid (20%) for 14 hours and the cooled solution saturated with ammonium sulphate, repeatedly extracted with ether and the extract washed with water and dried. After removing ether it was kept in a desiccator when it crystallised. Recrystallised from ether it melted at 135° , yield 3 g. (Found: C, 66.7; H, 5.77. $C_{13}H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 66.67, H, 5.9 per cent).

The *semicarbazone* of the above keto-acid was crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 233° , (decomp.). (Found: N, 14.4. $C_{14}H_{17}O_4N_3$ requires N, 14.4 per cent).

Ethyl $\alpha\beta$ -Dicyano- β -(p-methoxyphenyl)-propionate (II).—Anisaldehyde cyanohydrin (55 g.) was condensed with ethyl sodiocyanoacetate, prepared from ethyl cyanoacetate (48 g.) as before. The product was then poured into water and the solution acidified with hydrochloric acid. The separating oil was extracted with ether, the ethereal extract washed several times with water, then thoroughly with a dilute solution of sodium carbonate and after drying over calcium chloride evaporated. The dicyano-ester was distilled

as a viscous liquid at $225^{\circ}/5$ mm., which solidifies in a vacuum desiccator over sulphuric acid. It was crystallised from alcohol as colourless crystals, m.p. 81° , yield 30 g. (Found: N, 11.1. $C_{14}H_{14}O_3N_2$ requires N, 10.85 per cent).

The sodium carbonate washing from the ethereal solution gave an acid containing nitrogen and crystallised from alcohol in needle-shaped crystals, m.p. 226° . Since the quantity formed was too small an investigation of its constitution could not be made.

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